

CITY MAYOR FAIR DEBATE FRAMEWORK
WITH QUESTIONS BY THE FILIPINO CITIZENS

(Version 1)

Proposed by

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SUGGESTED FORMAT:

A debate with at least one hundred attendees.

- The list of the first 50 attendees shall come from one political party, while the second 50 attendees shall come from another political party.

No need to disclose the names of the 100 attendees. They shall wear two distinct colors representing who they support.

All attendees shall put their question on a piece of paper 15 minutes before the start of the debate. They shall put it in a box at the table in front of the two Mayor aspirants.

The first 10 questions shall be randomly chosen one by one by the two Mayor aspirants as debate questions. After 10 questions, all 100 guests can make a majority vote, whether to continue with another round of 10 questions.

There shall be two moderators of the debate: one from one political party, and the second from another political party.

The time limit to answer each question, and the rebuttal for each question, can follow the same format as the last Senatorial Debate organized by GMA7.

Suggested Time and Venue: City Hall at 8:00am from Monday to Friday. Via Facebook live so everyone can watch.

Note:

The format can be adjusted accordingly if there are three or more Mayor aspirants in a city. The same format above can be used by the Vice Mayor, Governor, Vice Governor, Congressman, Councilors, and Board Member aspirants.

Let's all end the political dynasty by allowing highly qualified Filipinos to debate fairly—no political machinery, no large number of supporters. Just mind, character, platforms, and vision for the Filipino people.

Para sa Pilipinas !!!

DETAILED DEBATE FORMAT:

Monday or Thursday:

All Mayor Aspirants shall be at front of their respective City Hall to discuss the format of the debate at 8:00am. Bring your own mic, and whiteboard (optional) to better explain the format.

If at least one is present, and the other is absent:

If one Mayor aspirant is absent for 15 minutes, the present aspirant can proceed with explaining his/her debate format for a maximum of one hour only. At 1pm the same day, he/she shall publicize in his/her official Facebook account the written format of the proposed debate format.

The public shall take note who is absent on Monday or Thursday to discuss the debate format.

If all are present:

All Mayor aspirants must publicly discuss the format they want. Each shall bring a mic with a whiteboard (optional) to better explain their proposed debate format. They shall speak impromptu on why their format should be used for the debate.

Toss a coin to decide who shall explain first.

After all aspirants publicly explain their proposed debate format, they can either decide to work together to have a final debate format, or they can upload their respective debate format in a local FB group with the highest member.

The debate format with the highest likes shall be used in the debate.

Other option: Adopt my proposed debate format, and just change the specific details.

Adopt my proposed debate format, and just change the following details:

The **yellow highlights** are my proposed details. While the **bold and underline** shall be the final that will be used in the debate proper. The **bold and underline** can change based on the input of each aspirant.

1. Number of attendees for each political parties: **50 attendees each**

- In case both parties have different attendees, just take the average and it shall be the final number of attendees for each.
- Example: One Mayor aspirant suggested 100 attendees, while the 2nd Mayor aspirant suggested 50 attendees.
 - $(100 + 50) / 2 = \mathbf{75\ attendees}$ each Mayor aspirant

2. Number of initial questions: **10**

- In case both parties have different numbers of proposed initial questions, just take the average and it shall be the final number of initial questions.
- Example: One Mayor aspirant suggested 20 initial questions, while the 2nd Mayor aspirant suggested 10 initial questions.
 - $(20 + 10) / 2 = \mathbf{15\ initial\ questions}$
 - Each question shall be answered ONE at a time by each aspirant. If the question is addressed to one Aspirant only, the other aspirant shall still answer the question.
 - Time limit: 5 minutes for each answer. 3 minutes rebuttal.
 - Example: Aspirant 1 answer the question #1 in 5 minutes, then the other aspirant has a maximum of 3 minutes rebuttal regardless whether his/her name is mentioned. Aspirant 2 answer the same question #1 in maximum of 5 minutes, and the other aspirant has a maximum of 3 minutes rebuttal whether or not his/her name is mentioned. In short, each has a maximum of 8 minutes for each question.
 - Just focus on the question and answer at a time to finish the first batch of 10 questions. Then all the attendees can have a majority vote whether to proceed in the next batch of 10 questions. The next day, each aspirant can have a press

conference in their own time to explain further in more than 8 minutes their respective answers in the debate.

- The moderator's role is to ensure that each question will be answered in 5 minutes, and 3 minutes for each rebuttal. After 8 minutes, they can just tell the aspirant to explain during their unlimited time the next day.
- Suggestion: A good moderator shall have at least 3 years arbitration experience. Each political party may consider the candidate's arbitration experience.

3. Number of minutes to answer each question, and number of minutes for each rebuttal.

- 5 minutes to answer each question, and 3 minutes for each rebuttal.
- If each aspirant has different suggested minutes, just take the average of their individual suggestion and it shall be the final during the debate proper.

THE DEBATE PROPER (Tuesday or Friday)

The next day after Monday or Thursday in which the details above are finalized.

Example: If the Mayor aspirants finalized the debate details on April 21 (Monday), the debate shall proceed the next day April 22 (Tuesday), or any day within the same week mutually agreed upon on Monday. If they decide on debate details on Thursday, they can have a debate on Monday next week.

In case there is a deadlock due to personality conflict, the aspirants can play bato bato pick in public, recorded via Facebook live for transparency. Best of five, and the one with the highest score shall decide whether the debate should be the same week or next week.

Non-negotiable: Do not prolong the debate into the 3rd week or 4th week after the format is finalized, as the election is fast approaching.

PROGRAM

- I. PRAYER and NATIONAL ANTHEM (15 minutes) 8:00am to 8:15am
- II. INTRODUCTION OF THE TWO MODERATORS EXPLAINING THE FINAL DEBATE FORMAT (15 minutes) 8:15 a.m. to 8:30 a.m.
- III. All Mayor aspirants shall introduce themselves in FIVE (5) minutes. Answer the question: Who they are and why they should be the next Mayor.
 - Anyone can volunteer who wants to come first. If both want to come first for the introduction part due to personality conflict, the two aspirants can play 'bato bato pick' on stage, best of five. The one with the highest score shall be the first to make a formal introduction.
- IV. START OF DEBATE. 10 questions in the first batch, with one question at a time. After 10 questions, all attendees shall make a majority decision whether to proceed with the next batch of 10 questions or not.

*Rule if there is a **duplicate** question:* The Mayor aspirant who picks the duplicate question will still publicly state the question. It will be skipped.

*Rule if there is a **similar** question:* Not duplicate, but there are some parts of the question that are quite different. Proceed with the debate.

- V. END OF DEBATE. Closing message of each aspirants maximum of five minutes. Like the closing message of the 2016 Presidential Debate.
 - Anyone can volunteer who wants to come first. If both want to come first for the introduction part, the two aspirants can play 'bato bato pick' on stage, one to five. The one with the highest score shall be the first to make a closing message.

Recommendation: If you have a recommendation to improve the above format, just leave a message in the comment section in social media and tag me.

If it's a totally different recommendation, just publish your own from scratch.

There might be some grammar mistakes, I will just fix it in the future in version 2.